

#1. Body length

#2. Carapace shape

#3. Rel. prosoma height

#4. Rel. paturon length

#5. Rel. fang length

#6. Eye size

#8. Anterior / posterior eyes ratio

#9. Rel. leg length

#10. Front leg difference

#11. Tibia / femur

#12. Leg width

#13. Femur thickening

#14. Front leg elongation

#15. Hind leg difference

0.566 log L3/L4 ratio 1.146
length=200

#16. Metatarsus elongation

#17. Tarsus elongation

#18. Opisthosoma shape

#19. Rel. opisthosoma height

#20. Spinneret length (PLS)

